

METHODS OF INTERACTIVE TEACHING OF STUDENTS OF NON- PHILOLOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. Among the extraordinary number of techniques for learning English, the quietness way strategy is of exceptional thought. One of the primary standards of this approach is that the educator plays out an aloof, "quiet" job during an EFL illustration. The reinforcements of this general strategy were created by Dr. Caleb Gattegno during the 60s. Having embraced this showing gadget first in quite a while classes, Gattegno states that in an English illustration the educator ought not to interfere with students and force his/her perspective on them. Being a flighty approach to educating, the quiet way is assumed to be shown involving actual articles in something new, for instance, tables, bars. The writer of the article focuses on one of the primary objectives of this approach-improvement of English talking abilities. The upside of the quiet way is that the instructor's language capability doesn't fundamentally influence the understudy's one at a non-philological college.

Keywords: non-philological university students, silent way (SW), the English language, a target language, methodology, a foreign language.

Introduction. In the current thousand years, for example in the third one, it is turning out to be progressively apparent that educating/learning English has turned into a fundamental peculiarity in the contemporary world. Therefore, the job of an English instructor is of incredible importance to get students propelled to accomplish objective language objectives. Achieving scholastic achievement in the EFL classroom is satisfactory on account of the mix of different systemic strategies, the quiet way technology is being one of them, specifically. Students' commitment to a great extent relies upon a language instructor's execution of a reasonable and proficient technique. In the circle of the language showing the quiet way (SW) is viewed as a technique which is believed to be instructed "quietly" from the instructor's side as a teacher ought to be pretty much as quiet as conceivable during an English language illustration while students, non-philological college students, specifically, ought to be propelled to talk a language however much as could reasonably be expected. As far as quiet way technique foundation the accentuation ought to be placed on the name of its originator, Dr. Caleb Gattegno. During the 1970s an Egyptian teacher C. Gattegno figured out how to deliver a thought that quiet could be viewed as a language showing framework, thus, the methodology was named "Quiet Way". As indicated by the traditional showing approach, students should fathom a foreign language by mimicking a teacher and remembering the new designs. By the by, Dr. Gattegno states "information is certifiably not an adaptable item, yet rather a build that should be effectively evolved through experience; thusly, the target of

training ought to be to raise students' mindfulness that there is information to be acquired, rather than to supply them with this information". [1]

J. Richards calls attention to that "The Silent Way Method is planned to actuate the student's force of mindfulness and ability to learn. Both info and result are more or less underestimated. While the dominance of sentence structure and jargon and the capacity to utilize language fluidly and precisely is at the center of language authority in the Silent Way, these require minimal point by point preplanning and will be the result of the exercises produced from the utilization of Cuisenaire poles and different things controlled by the educator". Many examinations are devoted to the quiet way. The approach of the quiet way depends on a few key standards: 1) students should be inventive and prepared to discover much-language-oriented data; 2) the method involved with learning is streamlined because of the execution of a few actual things; 3) students are urged to communicate their contemplations utilizing a target language; As it has been referenced over, the quiet way should be ideally utilized in mix with different strategies. Some quiet strategy studies recommend that it serves to ace just specific language abilities, jargon, punctuation, and elocution, in specific. With regards to clarifying the EFL syntax through the quiet way technique, the students need to discover on their own how the syntactic examples of an objective language are embraced. Without articulating even a solitary word the educator's assignment is to show the exceptional signs helping non-philological college students to deliver EFL articulations executing the language' designs performed by their instructor. Legitimate articulation abilities are no question vital for the students' talking practice since the primary objective of instructing/learning a foreign language is to get students to convey in the foreign language. The strategy is habitual to some extent carried out at a non-philological college. Instructors endeavor to have their students adapt to hardships they face during quiet way use.

The quiet way is viewed as an unusual approach to educating among non-philological college students since it is seldom utilized in the circle of advanced education. The quiet way procedure helps to remember a game-like method and, as a result, it could have alluded as an "elective language instructing 'framework'". With no guarantees commonly known, not many language students are naturally spurred to get drawn in into the information obtaining process, the greater part of them would lean toward being outwardly propelled to being self-roused. The creator of "Showing Foreign Languages in Schools: The Silent Way", Dr. Caleb Gattegno was well known for his offbeat showing strategy, regardless of whether it was utilized in showing dialects, variable-based math, or grown-up education. The instructor was known as "the world's most noteworthy instructor" for his drastically proficient and testing classes. He made a few entirely adaptable strategies that could be easily taken on by students to improve on the sentence structure and elocution intricacy of an objective language. These showing procedures transform troublesome dialect-situated issues into such bits of knowledge that teacher's clarification isn't needed. An instructor is just about as quiet as could be expected albeit a "quiet" instructor in the EFL classroom can oftentimes be misjudged by students. In this case, such an instructor's conduct is imagined as an educational

¹ Bruner, J. (1966). On knowing: Essays for the left hand. New York, NY: Atheneum.

method. Dr. Gattegno himself showed different dialects including Arabic, Hindi, English, and so forth utilizing SW in complete quiet from his side. Progressive English language examples where key SW strategic instruments are both completely and incompletely embraced are of incredible accomplishment among non-philological college students as the sound practice is extremely critical for them. Likewise, the quiet strategy is energetically prescribed to be utilized in showing an objective language even though it may appear to be a piece testing at the absolute starting point of the language course. Even though being a suitable method for objective language education, the quiet way technique is still generally condemned by certain teachers. They accept that making use of actual items, for instance, the shading bars during EFL instructing is thought of conceivable and pertinent just for youthful students while the non-philological college students require further developed and modern methodologies. An instructor coach in the field of showing English as a foreign language, John Pint states that "showing a language the Silent Way feels a lot of like driving a group of agents on a journey of revelation. [2] Like investigators, the students jump upon each piece of the riddle they find and as they set up them all, they become as certain as their educator in their dominance of the new dialect. Truth be told, it is to be expected for both instructor and students to feel thrilled after laboring for six hours during a serious course". Being a recognized SW trained professional, John Pint in his article "Caleb Gattegno and the quiet way" features that "though a run of the mill instructor may stroll into a classroom in light of an example plan and a reading material close by, a Silent Way educator may enter the room with a container of shaded bars and an extremely receptive outlook". Conventional showing gadgets depend on the possibility that educators should do most of the talking and be pretty much as dynamic as conceivable while clarifying language exercises. As far as the quiet way, the quietness is executed to focus on non-philological college students' mindfulness just as have them react and get inundated into rectification their missteps.

REFERENCES:

1. Bruner, J. (1966). On knowing: Essays for the left hand. New York, NY: Atheneum.
2. Cook, V. (2008). Second language learning and language teaching. London, England: Arnold.
3. Gattegno, C. (1976). The common sense of teaching foreign languages. New York, NY: Educational Solutions.
4. Harmer, J. (2001). The Practice of English Language Teaching. London: Longman.
5. <http://tecfaetu.unige.ch/staf/staf-e/marquis/travaux/staf15/Gattegno.html>
6. Richards, Jack C. (2013). Curriculum Approaches in Language Teaching: Forward, Central, and Backward Design. RELC Journal, 44(1) 5–33.
7. 12. Сысоев П.В., Евстигнеев М.Н. Современные учебные интернет-ресурсы в обучении иностранному языку // Иностранные языки в школе. 2008. № 6. 13.
8. Говорун С. В. Стратегии учебного аудирования // Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики. 2015. № 5-1(47). С. 76 – 81. 14.

² Cook, V. (2008). Second language learning and language teaching. London, England: Arnold.

9. Kapsargina S.A. The use of LMS Moodle to intensify the independent work of students in teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university / Азимут научных исследований: педагогика и психология. 2018. Том 7, №4(25). С.120-123. 15.
10. Khudoley N.V., Olentsova J.A. "New use of MOODLE tools for distance English language learning (experience of Krasnoyarsk state agrarian university)". 18th International Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference SGEM 2018, www.sgem.org, SGEM2018 Conference Proceedings, ISBN 78-619-7408-49-2 / ISSN 1314-2704, 2 July - 8 July, 2018, Vol. 18, Issue 5.4, 225-232 pp. 16.
11. Семенов А. А. Обучение студентов аудированию на иностранном языке с использованием интернет-ресурсов в неязыковом вузе // Вестник Российского университета кооперации. 2013. № 4(14). С. 107 – 109. 17.
12. Лопатина А.Я. Проблемы обучения аудированию на занятиях по иностранному языку в неязыковом вузе // Сборник научных трудов по материалам Международной научно-практической конференции в 2 частях: Наука, образование, общество: тенденции и перспективы. 2018. С. 25-29. 18.
13. Морозова А.Е. Способы преодоления трудностей при обучении аудированию студентов-международников исторического факультета Томского государственного университета (английский язык) // Балтийский гуманитарный журнал. 2018. Т. 7. № 2 (23). С. 297-300.
14. Чиркова В.М. Формирование аудитивных навыков у студентов-медиков, изучающих русский язык как иностранный // Карельский научный журнал. 2018. Т. 7. № 1 (22). С. 80-83.